

ISic3126

I.Sicily inscription 3126

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI329928

1. ἐνθάδε κίτε Σωτήρ
2. ζήσας τὸν βίον ἑαυτοῦ
3. ἀμένπτως, τελευτᾷ
4. τῆ πρ (ὀ) ιε καλ (ανδῶν) Αὐγούστων,
5. ζήσας ἔτη ν πλίο ἦτ-
6. τω, μετὰ τὴν ὑπατίαν
7. Θεοδοσίου τὸ ιβ καὶ
8. Βαλεντινιανοῦ τὸ β.
9. ἰρήνη τῆ ψυχῆ σου.
10. □ □ □
- 11.

Edition: PHI333751

1. ζήσας ἔτη ν πλίο (ν) ²⁶πλεῖον²⁶ ἦτ-
2. τω, . . .
- 3.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645467

PHI 329928

PHI 333751

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3126. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388163>